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Speech Communities

In the world that are different type of groups one might change from another but definitely they are using what we called language. Language itself can be sometimes difficult to learn and in fact it is a challenge when it comes to teach it. For many Linguistics that are different communities around the world and although they share the same language that are different variations in each community. These characteristics make population unique. But the question is what makes the speech unique from those communities?

Speech Communities work in different social categories stations and sometimes; of course, it can be discriminated some of the implications for social organizations as in human speech markers and others which are really evident on society aspects such as: age, sex, ethnicity, social class, and situations that can be really normal on basis of a speech. All of these behaviors and language elements can be established by participation in individuals or a set of shared norms in a way that they create the sense of community or uniformity. In order to have union, communities create patterns of behaviors that affect indirectly the language on a daily basis.

Some of the examples provided in the reading states people in New York though, the worldwide known big apple city is a huge community, most of the habitants have the same vocalic pronunciation, but they also have many differences on the social patterns. they share in other language stick elements; though they speak the same dialect a people from Southern British English Communities, they have many differences in tone, rhythm, pitch and phonology in general which creates a barrier of communication for people even though they share the same language which is English.

As a matter of fact, in English teaching occurs the same with to the levels were students find themselves when it comes to produce and react in their second language. According to the Common European Framework of Reference for languages, we have categories from A1 until C2, from the lowest which is A1, we can say that the person can understand some and limited vocabulary, therefore poor understanding and poor communication skills in general. In the other hand, we have the C2 level in which the person

is able to communicate in a very easy way, performing the four English skills with high proficiency, communication in general is well developed and managed successfully as a native.

In situations where different learners gather in groups, even though they do not feel that they are the same is speech community according to the CEFR, they accept that they are English speakers facing many differences and barriers in communication but at the end being able to communicate in the language in common which is English. A very normal situations in different groups of education or even in the same class where there are multilevel student population.

A group of a students is a speech community, people have one thing in common which is the use of a language. They learn different languages and they can identify themselves with that language that they are learning, they recognize, what their values are, their believes, and their knowledge rules the community. Second language learners although they are just a group of the students, they also have a set of norms and rules that they have to follow. The student's role allows them to interact with people who speak or who have a higher level of English that there might have some interferences; but the message is going to be still the same again. Therefore, what they are trying to do is to learn for others because if there is a enrichment of knowledge, for sure, they are going to take more advantages and the population which has the lowest performance on the second language are going to enhance their language skills by social interaction.

References:

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